

ISic1249

I.Sicily inscription 1249

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

accounts

Material

breccia

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

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Contributors

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Autopsy

2009.10.06

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del

ad ius pertinentes. Milan. At no.11

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5222

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5640 tab.2

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1249. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385679>